

Examining the Intricacies of Relation of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Attitude for Boosting Entrepreneurial Intentions among Higher Educational Institutions Students

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Abstract: This research has been undertaken to investigate the linkage of Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy (ESE) and Entrepreneurial Attitude (EA) with Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI). The study is based on survey of 589 students enrolled for entrepreneurial program/courses in higher education institutions. McGee et al (2009) scale has been used for ESE and Linan & Chen (2009) scale for EA and EI. This study is based SEM-PLS; results demonstrate a direct and significant linkage between ESE & EI (β : 0.697; $p \leq 0.001$) and between EA and EI (β : 0.282; $p \leq 0.001$). The focus on ESE and EA could help increase EI and induce them towards entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Entrepreneurial Attitude

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship has vital role to play in economy's success (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 1997) through creation of new businesses. As indicated by Nguyen (2020), it can give new insights to existing businesses through better input utilization or through investment opportunities (Voss et al., 2017). This has encouraged many countries to incorporate entrepreneurship as an integral part of their growth agenda (Nguyen, 2020). The root cause behind successful entrepreneurial activities is investment in new start-ups' (Afriyie and Boohene, 2014), which prospers through designing and starting entrepreneurial courses in HEIs (Webster and Ivanov, 2019). The youth of the nation can thus be exposed to the basic concepts of entrepreneurship and be prepared to start new ventures (Elnadi and Gheith, 2021). The intended course on entrepreneurship not only creates awareness about the different concepts of entrepreneurship (Falloon, 2019), but it also motivates the budding entrepreneurs to implement their new found ideas (Kim et al., 2018). The intensity of their willingness to implement their ideas depends upon EI

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(Hockerts, 2018). Thus, EI may be regarded as the most important step in the process of entrepreneurship (Taneja et al., 2023).

The concept of EI, i.e., the mindset to achieve entrepreneurial skills and values (Hockerts, 2018), is very complex (Yousaf et al., 2020) as various factors impact it directly or indirectly (Liñán et al., 2011; Hassan, 2020; Hoang, 2021). The present research examines the dimensions which influence EI of HEI students in India. Among the various factors identified from different studies (Liñán et al., 2011; Hassan, 2020; Hoang, 2021), self-efficacy and personal attitude are most important factors which influence individual's intentions to accomplish a task (Jung et al., 2001; Naktiyok et al., 2010; Campo, 2011; Nowinski et al., 2019; Elnadi and Gheith, 2021). A person with high personal efficacy and optimistic attitude towards entrepreneurship views challenges as the opportunities for growth (Kurczewska et al., 2020; Yousaf et al., 2020; Gill et al., 2021). New challenges require inculcating higher values and adopting more efficient and appropriate skill-set for entrepreneurial activities (Kolb, 1984). The model on "Planned behavior" proposed by Bandura (1986) considered individual attitude, self-efficacy and subjective norms to influence the actual behavior of an individual, but the impact is significant if mediated through individual's intentions.

2. Literature Review

The current study includes extensive review of existing literature for creating theoretical basis. For this research papers published in different reputed journals during the period 1976 to 2022 were considered, as they covered entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial attitude and entrepreneurial intention. These studies have also included entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial eco-system. Literature related to the concept of entrepreneurship during 1990s has undergone certain changes like the basic emphasis has shifted from the cognition approach to more constructive approach (Baker, Robinson and Kolb, 2012). We need to examine them in greater detail

2.1. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) and Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI)

The idea of self-efficacy is stranded in the cognitive social theory (Bandura 1997; Chen et al. 1998). Bandura (2012) stated that self-efficacy strongly influences the real behavior of the individuals. Despite the presence of alternatives (activities), the individuals put in their efforts to execute the chosen action (Maresch et al., 2016). The impression of self-efficacy is positioned in entrepreneurship (like by; Drnovšek et al., 2010; Pihie and Bagheri, 2013; Bae et al., 2014; Chowdhury et al., 2019). People tend to accept situations related with high self-beliefs (Uhm, Ko and Kim, 2019). Analogously, Chowdhury et al. (2019) opined that people are directed towards those occupations in which they possess

high self-efficacy rather than those where they feel incompetent. Self-efficacy is an action-specific aspect assisting in assessment of beliefs a person has in coping up with personal and external challenges to pursue entrepreneurship (Boyd and Vozikis, 1994; Salloum and Azoury, 2011; Ineson et al., 2013; Yousaf et al., 2020). Hence, self-efficacy is a vital parameter and therefore a suitable construct for the current study.

Martínez (2011) analysed the impact of ESE on EI with gender as moderating variable. The results reflected that ESE and EI were not moderated by gender; rather ESE was directly linked to EI. Pihie and Bagheri (2013) found significant influence of ESE on EI. Forster and Grichnik (2013) pointed out a direct & strong connection among Empathy, ESE and EI (Tiwari, Bhat and Tikoria, 2017). Yousaf et al. (2020) reflected the relevance of ESE and EA in determining EI of the individuals, though both the variables were studied in terms of mediation of entrepreneurial education (EE) and EI. Elnadi and Gheith (2021) found that mediating role of ESE was strong and significant in examining the linkage between entrepreneurial ecosystem and EI. Though, there is vast literature highlighting relation of ESE with EI, but very few link ESE with EI directly.

Furthermore Oosterbeek et al. (2008) showed some contradicting results. In addition, Newman et al. (2019) stated that the association between ESE and EI can show different results if examined in developing countries, like India. Though, there are studies relating self-efficacy with intention, but most of them examine it as a moderating or mediating variable (Taneja et al., 2023). The present study is intended towards examining the direct association between ESE and EI, related to developing nations like India.

2.2. Entrepreneurial Attitude and Entrepreneurial Intentions

Attitude is important especially in regard to an individual's choice of entering into a profession or doing a particular task (Palalic et al., 2020). Extant literature has confirmed that attitude might play a greater role in determining the intentions of the people (Liu et al., 2019; Adu et al., 2020; Del Giudice et al., 2021; Valencia-Arias et al., 2022). Attitude, with due attention and proper nurturing, can be very crucial in shaping the individual's perception towards becoming an entrepreneur (Nyamunda and Van Der Westhuizen, 2020; Del Giudice et al., 2021). Thus, a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship can be considered as a critical influencer in EI (Nowiński et al., 2019; Yousaf et al., 2020).

Although ESE has a direct influence on the EI of the students (Nowinski et al., 2019; Elnadi and Gheith, 2021), but attitude towards becoming an entrepreneur has also impacted EI (Mahfud et al., 2020; Yousaf et al., 2020). Jena (2020) showed that a progressive attitude towards entrepreneurship has impacted EI positively. Bae et al. (2014) regarded EA as true predictor of the EI, while von Graevinitz et al. (2010) have shown

mixed results linking EA with EI. However, limited studies have shown negative results of EA with EI (Do Paco et al., 2013; Marques et al., 2012).

It was also observed that, previous studies have focused upon mediation or moderating role of EA with EI (Jena, 2020; Mahfud et al., 2020). The current study linked EA with EI, not personal attitude of the students as considered by (Jena, 2020). In view of these diversities it was thought to conduct a study relating ESE and EA with EI.

Dempsey and Jennings (2014) discussed the association between Entrepreneurial education (EE) and ESE concerning gender perspective and it was implied that more studies should be carried out to examine the linkage among EE, ESE, and EI in general and ESE and EI in particular (Nowinski et al., 2017; Jena, 2020). Though, earlier studies have examined the linkage of EE, ESE, and EI (Hoang, 2021; Nowinski et al., 2019; Hockerts, 2018), there are rare that have examined the direct relationship of ESE with EI (Naktiyok et al., 2010; Martínez, 2011; Hassan, 2020). Moreover, majority of these studies were carried out in developed nations, under similar cultural backdrop. The present study has tried to fill up the gap of examining the impact of ESE on EI in a developing nation like India. Additionally, the study has also tried to investigate the direct influence of EA with EI.

This study is designed to examine the relationship between Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy (ESE) and Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) and to examine the linkage between Entrepreneurial Attitude (EA) and Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI). The related hypothesis is as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (ESE) positively influences Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) of the students

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relation between Entrepreneurial Attitude (EA) and Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) of the students

3. Methodology

The research has used National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) for short listing the top 100 educational institutions. NIRF is ranking framework, setup in 29th September 2015 and approved by Minister of Human Resource Development (MHRD). The study has adopted multi-level sampling procedure, initially selecting top 100 rated institutions using NIRF ranking. In the next stage from these 16 HEIs from three regions of North India (i.e. Punjab, Haryana and NCR) were selected and finally, 10 institutions where students were offered entrepreneurship programs/ courses were selected. From a total of 1000 students, 589 responses received. The study used McGee et al. (2009) multidimensional scale for measuring the ESE with 19 items. Entrepreneurial Intention covers both future (EFI) and

present intentions (EI). EA was measured using Linan and Chen (2009) scale, due to its high reliability of the construct (Cronbach alpha i.e. 0.94). Students were asked to rate on five-point scale where 5 stated as strongly agree and 1 is strongly disagree. The study has used SEM-PLS for framing and analyzing the model.

Figure 1: Conceptual model indicating association between ESE, EA, and ESE

4. Findings

The model contains two independent variables i.e. ESE and EA and only dependent variable is EI. Internal consistency was checked through composite reliability and Cronbachs’ Alpha α . Further, to check convergent validity we used average variance extracted (AVE). Additionally, the study has measured effect of removed exogenous variable on the dependent variable by calculating F-square. The value of $f^2 \geq 0.15$ indicating medium-large effect of exogenous variable (if removed) on dependent variable (Cohen, 1988). To check the whether there exists collinearity, variance inflation factor (VIF) was used. The values greater than 3 shows high co linearity, since all the value as depicted in Table 1 are <3 , we can infer that there is no issue of related with collinearity.

This research examines relation of ESE and EI, second, and of EA with EI. The outcomes highlight that a strong (direct) and significant relationship exists between ESE and EI with β - value of 0.697 ($p \leq 0.001$). This further state that study’s H1 i.e. Hypothesis 1: “ESE positively influences EI of the students” is empirically supported. ESE can be regarded as important construct in accurately predicting the EI of the students (Elnadi and Gheith, 2021). The past studies have given a surety for the direct linkage of ESE and EI (Nowinski et al., 2019; Hockerts et al., 2018; Adu et al., 2020). The linkage between EA and EI was also significant which shows EA also has a direct influence on EI β - value 0.282

($p \leq 0.001$). Thus, our second objective is also fulfilled with H2 Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relation between EA and EI of the students is also empirically supported. Thus, one's attitude has a greater role to play in influencing the intentions of the individual (Bandura, 1977).

Table 1: Construct reliability, validity and VIF

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	F ²				
Entrepreneurial Attitude	0.686	0.734	0.822	0.609	0.245				
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.602	0.618	0.833	0.713					
Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.876	0.899	0.909	0.666	1.497				
Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)									
A1	A2	A3	EI	EI	ESE1	ESE2	ESE3	ESE4	ESE5
1.278	1.412	1.344	1.227	1.227	1.889	2.304	2.042	2.224	1.840

Table 2 indicates that R² value is 0.735 and that of adjusted R² is 0.734. The R² is considered to be a good measure for the model fit, it is inferred that the variation is explained by independent variable. Thus, 73.5 percent of the variation in dependent variable (EI) is explained by the two predictors, ESE and EA.

Table 2: Path Coefficients and R square

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.697	0.698	0.024	29.655	0.000***
Entrepreneurial Attitude -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.282	0.282	0.033	8.509	0.000***
Model Fit	R ²			Adjusted R ²	
	0.735			0.734	

Note: *** $p \leq 0.001$.

5. Discussion and Implications

The study has tried to contribute to our understanding, through examining the direct linkage of ESE with EI and of EA with ESE. The outcomes highlight that ESE and EA perform a significant role in determining the EI of the students enrolled in entrepreneurial programs/courses. Bandura (1977 and 1984) regarded self-efficacy as a precondition for behavioral control (Adu et al., 2020). The important outcome of the current analysis is that

all the sub-dimensions related to ESE in the present study play a vital role in determining EI (Hockerts, 2018). This could help in framing policies to outline training programs for increasing ESE of the students (Gill et al., 2021). Therefore, all the sub-dimensions of the ESE are significant ($p \leq 0.001$) which shows that the construct (Appendix 1), i.e., ESE needs to get more attention as compared to other constructs of EI. This lends support to H1, i.e., Hypothesis 1: ESE positively influences EI of the students. Another important contribution is concerned with the importance of EA in forming EI. The outcomes of the study indicate that there is a positive, but less significant relationship between EA and EI ($\beta: 0.282; p \leq 0.001$). According to Bandura (1977) attitude plays a vital role in forming actual behavior of the individual. Thus, various factors, like providing proper ecosystem (Elnadi and Gheith, 2021) and role models could play a significant role in forming positive EA with regard to EI. Thus, the study, H2, i.e., Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relation between EA and EI of the students.

Figure 2: Association of ESE and EA with EI

This study highlights the importance of EA and ESE in forming EI of the students. Although all the sub-constructs of ESE are important, but planning ESE2 turns out to be the most important sub-construct with outer loadings (0.847), given in appendix 1 followed by ESE1, ESE4, ESE3, ESE5. As confirmed in the study of Nowinski et al. (2017), that planning forms a significant part in forming the EI of the students. The current

paper has also proposed that studies related to the ESE would benefit from the more reliable scale of McGee et al. (2009). In case of EA, A3 i.e. attractiveness turns out to be an important sub-item. Bandura (1984) in the Theory of Planned behavior regarded both “Self-efficacy” and “Personal attitude” as important constructs which contribute to intentions of the individual. Thus, the outcome of this research has importance for policies pertaining to entrepreneurship adoption in India and highlighting those factors that lead to a positive EI.

Furthermore, the current study can assist in developing courses appropriate for our future generations by addressing the short comings in the existing methodology. The governments of many European countries have developed different plans to support entrepreneurship for university graduates and country like Poland has introduced it at the secondary level (Egerová et al., 2016). But in a country like India, there is a difference in opinion, regarding the content of such programs and the academic level where it can be incorporated (Taneja et al., 2023). This study emphasis the need to think beyond the tradition method and recommends for strategies in addition to the academic programs.

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Appendix 1

Paths coefficient and Indicator loadings

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Entrepreneurial Attitude -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.282	0.282	0.033	8.509	0.000***
Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.697	0.698	0.024	29.655	0.000***
Outer Loadings	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
A1 <- Entrepreneurial Attitude	0.693	0.692	0.042	16.607	0.000***
A2 <- Entrepreneurial Attitude	0.787	0.787	0.024	33.336	0.000***
A3 <- Entrepreneurial Attitude	0.852	0.851	0.016	53.597	0.000***
EI <- Entrepreneurial Intention	0.878	0.879	0.008	103.526	0.000***
EI <- Entrepreneurial Intention	0.810	0.809	0.023	34.538	0.000***
ESE1 <- Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.838	0.838	0.012	71.806	0.000***
ESE2 <- Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.847	0.846	0.013	63.473	0.000***
ESE3 <- Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.802	0.802	0.021	38.008	0.000***
ESE4 <- Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.822	0.821	0.018	44.789	0.000***
ESE5 <- Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.769	0.768	0.022	34.331	0.000***

Note: $p \leq 0.001$ ***.

Discriminant Validity

	Entrepreneurial Attitude	Entrepreneurial Intention	Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy
Entrepreneurial Attitude	0.780		
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.582	0.845	
Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	0.429	0.819	0.816

Note: Values on diagonal represent the square root of the AVE.